

Effect of salinity on root growth characteristics of rice.

Variety	Salinity level (dS/m)	Maximum root length (%)	Root volume (cm ³ /plant)	Root dry matter (g/plant)	Water content of plant (%)	Relative water content of leaves (%)	Na concentration in roots (% DM)
<i>Tillering stage</i>							
CSR-1	2.5	30.2	150.0	6.4	87.7	97.4	0.52
	5.4	29.0	148.1	6.8	86.7	96.3	0.66
	12.7	31.6	145.9	7.6	85.9	95.3	1.08
M1-48	2.5	30.5	102.5	4.1	87.1	94.8	0.65
	5.4	30.5	87.8	3.3	82.6	89.9	0.93
	12.7	18.3	63.0	1.8	68.0	76.1	1.45
<i>Flowering stage</i>							
CSR-1	2.5	31.1	180.6	8.2	86.8	97.9	0.54
	5.4	28.7	179.1	8.3	86.0	95.1	1.99
	12.7	30.8	175.6	9.1	85.9	90.2	2.28
M1-48	2.5	32.0	115.1	4.8	87.0	96.3	0.79
	5.4	30.5	98.3	3.5	83.0	88.1	2.38
	12.7	19.6	62.9	1.6	65.0	76.0	2.71
LSD (0.05)		0.8	1.7	0.4	1.2	1.6	0.32

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Yield response of Basmati rice to applied P at different soil P values

G. Hassan, E. H. Chaudhary, S. M. Mian, K. H. Gill, and A. A. Sheikh, Rapid Soil Fertility Survey and Soil Testing Institute, Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

We measured yield of Basmati 385 in response to 0, 33, 66, and 99 kg P/ha in 32 farmers' fields in West Punjab, Pakistan. All treatments received 125-62-4.2 kg NKZn/ha. Soils ranged from loam to clay loam, 8.0 to 8.4 pH, 0.84 to 3.1 dS/m EC, 3 to 20 mg Olsen's P/kg, 0.51 to 1.03% organic matter, and 132 to 351 mg ammonium acetate extractable K/kg.

We transplanted 35-d-old rice seedlings at 25 × 25-cm spacing. All of the P and K and half of the N was applied at last puddling, Zn at 10 d after transplanting, and the remaining N at panicle initiation. Yield was recorded at 14% moisture level. Data collected during 1990 and 1991 dry seasons (DS) were pooled and grouped into categories of low, medium, satisfactory, and adequate based on Olsen's P values. Each category was statistically analyzed and average values tabulated.

Yield increased significantly up to 33 kg P/ha for all soil P test values, but significant responses to the next higher dose was observed only when test values were less than or equal to 11 mg P/kg (see table).

Marginal rate of return (MRR) is target return from the last dollar invested on the purchase of an input. Yield data were used for curve-fitting at MRR values of 0.5, 0.1, and 1.5 to establish P rate recommendations for a given soil P test value (see figure). These curves facilitate site-specific recommendations on P use for Basmati 385 that accommodate soil P status and economic motives of a farmer. ■

Average yield of Basmati 385 at different soil P levels under graded doses of P. West Punjab, Pakistan, 1990 and 1991 DS.

P applied (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) at soil P test value of			
	7 mg/kg (9) ^a	8-11 mg/kg (11)	12-15 mg/kg (7)	15 mg/kg (5)
0	2.6 c	3.4 c	3.6 b	4.0 b
33	3.3 b	4.1 b	3.9 ab	4.6 a
66	3.8 a	4.3 ab	4.3 a	4.5 ab
99	3.9 a	4.5 a	4.0 ab	4.3 ab

^aFigures in parentheses are number of experiments. 18 were performed in 1990 and 14 in 1991. Figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 0.05 LSD.

Plant water content and relative water content of leaves in both varieties, but especially in M1-48, showed a downward trend with increase in salinity and age. Sodium concentration in roots increased significantly as salinity increased. Variety M1-48 accumulated more sodium than CSR-1 during tillering and flowering stages. ■

P recommendation (kg P/ha)

Soil test relationship curves for P at various marginal rate of return (MRR) values.